

VAPOUR PRESSURES OF AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS.

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A new method has been devised to determine the vapour pressure of liquids and solutions. Compared to other methods this method has been found to be simple, rapid and to yield accurate and reproducible results. Observed values of vapour pressures of aqueous solutions of $ZnCl_2$, $Ca(CNS)_2$, $Zn(CNS)_2$ and H_3PO_4 are recorded. From thermodynamical considerations osmotic pressures of these solutions have been calculated. Experimental results suggest a strong affinity between water and these salts which is in agreement with the properties of these substances.

In connection with certain work which is in progress in this laboratory, owing to lack of data in literature it was found necessary to determine the vapour pressures of aqueous solutions of zinc chloride, calcium thiocyanate, zinc thiocyanate and phosphoric acid. Among numerous methods developed for its accurate measurement, the 'dynamic' methods are more tedious than the 'static' and demand an extremely careful manipulation. Although the results obtained by the dynamic method are considered more trustworthy, the static methods have been employed with great success. After reviewing the works of Dieterici (*Wied. Ann.*, 1893, 80, 47), Smits (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1902, 39, 385), Tower (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 30, 1219), Wood (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1915, 11, 29), and Perman and Saunders (*ibid.*, 1923, 19, 112), it seemed possible to devise an alternative method, which could be simple, rapid and yet reasonably accurate. The method finally adopted is described in the following section.

EXPERIMENTAL.

All reagents employed in this investigation were analytical reagents (certified B. D. H.). Solutions of various concentrations of the salts were prepared by weight dilution from saturated solutions carefully filtered through a sintered glass funnel. Syrupy phosphoric acid was used for preparing solutions of that acid. The strength of the solution was determined by the estimation of both the components of the salt and only those solutions were employed where the concentrations as determined by the estimation of both the ions agreed within 0.2%. Zinc was estimated with potassium ferrocyanide using methyl red as an adsorption indicator (Tananaew and Georgofini, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1936, 107, 92). Potassium palmitate method (Hamer, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1935, 54, 205) was employed

to estimate calcium. Chlorides were estimated with silver nitrate by the simplified potentiometric method (Callan and Horrobin, *ibid.*, 1921, 47, 329) and the thiocyanates by the use of the same reagent but with ferric alum as an indicator. Wilkie's method (*ibid.*, 1909, 28, 68) was adopted to estimate phosphoric acid.

Vapour pressures of these solutions were measured in a specially constructed apparatus (Fig. 1). A flask A (200 c.c.) was connected by a mercury sealed ground glass joint B to the bulb C, the top of which was sealed to a 10 c.c. burette E with a glass stop-cock D, while a side-tube led through another mercury sealed joint G to the mercury manometer IJ. Both the joints B and G were fitted with steel springs to keep them tight. The manometer was made of a wide tubing ($d=1$ cm.) to minimise meniscus errors in reading and its lower end passed through a well fitting rubber stopper into a glass bottle H serving as a mercury reservoir. The reservoir was connected through K to the vacuum system. The limb I of the manometer was connected to a phosphoric pentoxide tube M through a ground glass joint L and a tap W. The other end of the P_2O_5 tube was connected to the vacuum system. All the ground joints and taps were greased with 'apiezon' grease.

FIG. 1.

The apparatus could be separated into three parts R N M L permanently attached to the vacuum pump, Q H L G which carried the manometer, and E C B A which contained the solution under investigation. The piece E C B A was the only one which required to be cleansed and dried before each determination.

The apparatus was assembled together and immersed in the thermostat as shown in Fig. 1 with water upto the line XX'. A drop of mercury was introduced into the bore of the stop-cock D to remove air from there, 10 c.c. of the solution were placed in the burette E.

The interior of the apparatus was evacuated until a hard metallic sound of the pump indicated a good vacuum inside it. With tap W closed, Q was opened to air through T to let sufficient mercury rise into the manometer IJ. By the use of a travelling microscope the level in the two limbs was ascertained to be the same. The apparatus was left undisturbed for a couple of hours when no alteration in the two levels showed a good vacuum inside the apparatus. Now D is opened to let in about 7 c.c. of the solution into A. This causes a shift in the levels of mercury in the two limbs of the manometer. Readings of both the levels are taken at regular intervals until they show no change. The difference between the two levels gives the vapour pressure of the solution.

By appropriate manipulation mercury is withdrawn from the manometer into the reservoir and the tap W is kept open for 1 minute to connect the solution in A to the evacuating system. This causes the solution to 'boil' and ensures the escape of any dissolved gases from it. Mercury is reintroduced into the manometer and the evacuation from the limb I continued until a good vacuum is obtained above the mercury level in it. The difference in the two levels was again noted. This second reading is invariably lower than the first one and accounts for any dissolved gas in the solution. The process of 'boiling' is repeated and a third reading is taken. The second and the third observations are usually found to be identical. If they differ from each other another reading is similarly taken. At the end of the experiment the solution in A was analysed to determine its strength.

By this method vapour pressures of various different solutions and liquids (of which the vapour pressures are accurately known) were determined. Table I records the results of such measurements and it shows a satisfactory agreement between the observed and the 'standard' values.

TABLE I.

Substance.	Temp.	Vapour pressure.	
		Int. Crit. Tables.	Author.
Water	25.0°	23.50 mm.	23.55 mm.
Water	26.0°	24.987	25.10
38 % H ₂ SO ₄	25.0°	14.50	14.57
55 % H ₂ SO ₄	25.0°	6.15	6.18

This agreement justified the final adoption of this method for measuring the vapour pressures of liquids and solutions.

Evacuation was done with the aid of a vacuum oil pump with an electric motor and a pressure of 0.02 mm. was recorded by Pirani gauge when evacuation was considered to be complete. All the experiments were carried out in a water thermostat electrically heated and regulated at $25 \pm 0.02^\circ$.

Vapour pressures of the three salts and of phosphoric acid are recorded in Tables II-V.

TABLE II.
Zinc chloride at 25°.

% by wt.	Concentration. Molality. <i>m.</i>	Vapour pressure (mm. of Hg.).	Osmotic pressure (atmos.).
21.05	1.965	20.75	171.7
42.42	5.405	16.45	500.0
55.01	8.973	11.00	1081.0
57.62	9.977	9.70	1277.0
60.00*	11.01	8.10	1556.0
62.81	12.40	7.15	1760.0
65.00*	13.62	5.00	2330.0
67.51	15.25	4.20	2626.0
70.00*	17.12	2.90	3252.0
73.03	19.89	1.30	4650.0
75.02	22.04	0.60	5560.0

* Menezies and Boving (8th Int. Con. App. Chem, Rep., 1912).

TABLE III.
Calcium thiocyanate at 25

% by wt.	Concentration. Molality.	Vapour pressure.	Osmotic pressure.
8.69	0.6092	22.80	14.63
19.52	1.552	20.70	174.6
31.32	2.929	17.30	430.3
40.48	4.355	12.20	937.0
51.13	6.699	7.70	1617.3
57.98	9.835	3.40	2873.0

TABLE IV.

Zinc thiocyanate at 25

% by wt.	Concentration. Molality.	Vapour pressure.	Osmotic Pressure.
8.778	0.5302	22.80	41.44
19.07	1.132	22.20	99.87
26.56	1.993	21.75	105.7
34.42	2.894	20.25	205.9,
38.70	3.477	19.45	262.6
42.10	4.021	18.80	310.1

TABLE V.

Phosphoric Acid at 25°.

% by wt.	Concentration. Molality.	Vapour pressure.	Osmotic pressure.
12.92	1.513	22.0	89.8
28.38	4.041	20.8	166.6
38.81	6.469	19.0	291.8
57.49	13.79	12.65	873.1
72.12	26.39	6.45	1917.0
75.93	32.18	5.30	2231.0
77.91	35.97	4.40	2537.0
80.83	43.00	3.40	2976.0
83.85	52.65	2.70	3381.0
86.80	67.05	1.80	4101.0
89.15	83.77	0.90	5335.0

DISCUSSION.

Relation between vapour pressure and concentration is shown graphically in Fig. 2, and it is evident from the nature of the curves that the lowering in vapour pressure is not proportional to the concentration of the solute. With zinc thiocyanate, however, the lowering in the vapour pressure seems to be almost proportional to the concentration of the salt in solution.

FIG. 2.

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to H_3PO_4 , $Zn(CNS)_2$, $ZnCl_2$ and $Ca(CNS)_2$.

From a knowledge of the vapour pressures of these solutions their osmotic pressures can be calculated. Porter (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1908, **79**, 519; **80**, 457) evolved an equation relating vapour pressure to osmotic pressure of a solution from purely thermodynamic considerations. The form of equation given by Porter has been integrated and rearranged as follows by Wood (*loc. cit.*).

$$Ps(1-\infty P/2) = RT \log_e \frac{\pi_0}{\pi_\pi} = C(\pi_0 - \pi_\pi) + (b-s)(\pi_0 - \pi_\pi)$$

where,

P = the osmotic pressure of the solution when it is under its own pressure.

s = shrinkage in volume of solution when 1 g. of solvent is removed from an infinite volume.

∞ = compressibility of water at T° absolute.

π_0 = vapour pressure of water under its own v.p.

π_π = vapour pressure of solution under its own v.p.

C = concentration of solution.

b = constant in Callender's gas equation.

R and T have their usual significance.

In applying the equation it is permissible to drop the last term since both b and s are nearly equal to unity. Shrinkage s is calculated from density data from an expression given by Callendar (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1908, **A**, **80**, 466).

With the aid of this equation, osmotic pressures of all the solutions have been calculated and it is found that excepting in the case of zinc thiocyanate, the calculated values of the osmotic pressure are of the order of a few thousand of atmospheres. What exactly such high values of osmotic pressure mean is difficult to conceive but it is clear that if such solutions were separated by semipermeable membranes from the pure solvent, enormously high pressures will have to be applied to the solution to prevent osmosis. The figures in other words indicate the strong affinity which zinc chloride, calcium thiocyanate and phosphoric acid have towards water, an indication which is in agreement with other properties of these substances.